

INFLUENCE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND CLASSROOM CLIMATE

Ruizsparza Flores BETSABÉ

University Regional Of North, *Juárez, Chihuahua, México*

ABSTRACT

At present, we live in a fast-paced world, there is more communication thanks to technology, but emotional intelligence towards other human beings could be damaging, in addition, in the professional teaching practice it cannot be forgotten that students are the pillar of each institution, not only learn theories and practices but also behaviors and values, this is where the intention of this article lies, through the literary search of the subject to have a broad vision of emotional intelligence and climate in the classroom; After reading it, it can be said that to the extent that the teacher analyzes, understands and puts into practice Emotional Intelligence in the classroom, students could present better academic performance and professional performance once they graduate. To be a teacher is to be an example, all this from the review of authors such as Mayer and Salovey (1997), Fernandez Berrocal (2010) and Aranda (2010).

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, classroom climate, teachers, college, emotions.

Introduction

Mayer and Salovey (1990) defined the concept of "emotional intelligence" for the first time, although later in 1997 they reformulated their original idea, giving more importance to cognitive components and the ability to reflect on emotions.

From the EI-ability model (Mayer and Salovey, 1997) a hierarchical structure of cognitive capacities is proposed for the adaptive management of emotions, that is, an EI is: perceive, facilitate, understand and manage or regulate emotions

For Rodriguez Vitae (s.f.) The learning climate is interaction, communication between those who are within the teaching and learning process, this must occur between the teacher and the students and viceversa, as well as -. Within this climate, harmony, trust, security, and respect must prevail, so that students can freely express themselves, make known any concerns or doubts in favor of obtaining true learning.

School climate refers to the qualities of the school environment that are experienced by teachers, administrators, students, and other members of the school community.¹ It is the impressions of these individuals as they experience school policies, practices, and procedures. (The Aspen Institute, 2021)

The positive emotions of teachers can improve their well-being, as well as the adjustment of their students (Birch & Ladd, 1996) and the increase of these positive emotions can facilitate the creation of a classroom climate that favors learning (Sutton & Whealey, 2003). Likewise, the generation of positive emotions improves the well-being and happiness of the students (Seligman, 2005).

In this way, that teachers learn to maintain positive emotional states and reduce the impact of negative ones can be reflected in greater teacher well-being and better adjustment of their students (Fernández - Berrocal & Ruiz - Aranda, 2008).

Previously, research by Fernández-Berrocal (2010) focused on analyzing the relationship between emotional intelligence and the teacher's personal adjustment, indicate that the teacher's emotional intelligence predicts the level of burnout they suffer (Brackett, Palomera & Mojsa, in press ;Extremera, Fernández - Berrocal and Durán, 2003).

After reading and analyzing the subject in question, a gap that was found is trying to delve into the conflicts that can arise in the classroom due to the fact of presenting negative coping and generating a hostile climate in the classroom at the university level, since, after all the review in studies, only one was found that will take into account the conflict as a problem due to the lack of socio-emotional competencies.

The problem studied refers that a school with a good school climate is a professional organization where there is collaboration between directors and teachers, in which families and students participate, and in which respectful treatment among children and appreciation for others is promoted. (LLECE, 2012).

As a justification, in schools it is no longer enough to achieve a good performance of the students, the success of the teaching staff is also linked to developing people integrated into society, with social and emotional tools that allow them to face the challenges of daily life (Fernández – Berrocal & Ruiz – Aranda, 2008a)

According to Cabello & Fernández-Berrocal (2010) It implies that teachers develop a greater capacity to identify, understand, regulate and think with emotions intelligently, they will have more resources to get emotionally more prepared students and to better cope with stressful events that arise often in the educational context.

It is intended to inquire about the level of relationship that is established between the teacher's Emotional Intelligence and the emotional classroom climate, which is usually a reflection of the teacher's abilities through the existing

literature. Educational transformation is a necessity in order to make changes in an education system to improve the quality and competitiveness of education at the international level. This is because education is one of the most important activities of any country. In ensuring the success of educational transformation, all important aspects of educational development planning should be looked at, especially in strengthening the physical, academic, and social aspects of a school. (Azlin Norhaini, Mohd Zabil & Hamid, 2021)

TYPE OF STUDY

According to López Fernández, et. to the. (2019) Theoretical methods such as logical historical and synthetic analytics were used, and from empyrean, to the analysis of documents, which allowed arriving at the proposed methodology. The fundamental results are associated with a sequential structure, of strict compliance to ensure that the instrument is validated and thus obtain results supported by science.

Due to its importance and complexity of application, instrument validation is considered a type of study within intervention studies, that is, at the same level as experimental, quasi-experimental, among others.

Analysis technique

Table 1.- Axes of conceptual cartography (Tobón, 2012a) Analysis axis
Central question

- Notion What is the etymology of the concept of knowledge management, its historical development and the current definition?

The word 'intelligence' comes from the Latin *intelligentia* or *intellēctus*, which in turn comes from the verb *intellegere* - a compound term of *inter* ("between") and *legere* ("read, choose") - which means to understand or perceive.

Emotion (from Lat. *Emoveo*, *emotum* = moved, disturbed) is an involuntary impulse, originated in response to environmental stimuli, which

induces feelings in humans and animals, and which triggers automatic reaction behaviors.

The word classroom comes from the Latin *aula* and this from the Greek $\alpha\upsilon\lambda\eta$. In Roman times, it referred to fenced courtyards where ceremonies were held.

- **Categorization** To which major category (or class) does the concept of knowledge management belong?

Emotional Intelligence: Mayer & Salovey define emotional intelligence as “the ability to perceive, value and express emotions accurately; the ability to access and generate feelings that facilitate thinking; the ability to understand emotion and emotional awareness; and the ability to regulate emotions and promote emotional and intellectual growth ”(Mayer & Salovey, 1997: 10).

- **Differentiation** From what other close concepts and that are in the same category does the concept of knowledge management differ?
- **Socio-emotional skills**

Table 1.- Axes of conceptual cartography (Tobón, 2012a). Continuation
Analysis axis Central question

- **Classification** In which subclasses or types is the concept of knowledge management classified?
- **Emotions**
- **Coping**
- **Linkage** How is knowledge management linked to certain theories, social-cultural processes and epistemological references that are outside the category?
- **Quality of education**
- **Educational reforms**
- **Methodology** What are the minimum methodological elements involved in the knowledge management approach?
- **360 degree survey**

- Likert scales
(they are applied in the present study)
- Exemplification What could be a relevant and pertinent example of the application of the concept of knowledge management?

The teacher’s Emotional Intelligence and the emotional climate, which is usually a reflection of the teacher’s abilities. It is worth mentioning that a school with a good school climate is a professional organization where there is collaboration between directors and teachers, in which families and students participate, and in which respectful treatment among children and appreciation for others is promoted. (LLECE, 2012)

SELECTION CRITERIA

Articles were searched in the following databases: redalyc, scielo, EBSCO, google academics using words such as „intelligence”, „emotional intelligence”, „classroom climate”, the information was also searched in blogs and web pages as psicoactiva.com.

Author	Year of publication	Title	Type of article	Synthesis
Elena Balongo González, Rosario Mérida Serrano	2016	The classroom climate in work projects. Create learning environment s to include	Validation Indexed	This paper presents the main results of the research carried out in a public school in a town in Córdoba (Spain). A methodology

		child diversity		based on student research
F. Javier Murillo, Reyes Hernández- Castilla, Cynthia Martínez-Garrido	2016	What happens in classrooms where children do not learn? Qualitative study of ineffective classrooms in Latin America	Original Indexed	The aim of this research is to understand what happens in these classrooms. For this, an in- depth study was carried out in which eight particularly ineffective classrooms were analyzed in as many Latin American countries (Colombia, Chile, Cuba, Ecuador, Spain, Panama, Peru and Venezuela). The results point to six major factors

of classroom ineffectiveness: a) teaching strategies in the classroom; b) use of time; c) attention to diversity; d) evaluation strategies; e) classroom climate; and f) the classroom as a physical space and its resources.

<p>Nancy Noemí Gutiérrez-Anguiano, Alicia Alelí Chaparro Caso López</p>	<p>2019</p>	<p>Evidence of reliability and validity of a scale for the self-evaluation of teaching practices in secondary school</p>	<p>Validation Indexed</p>	<p>The objective of this study was to develop and validate a scale for the self-evaluation of teaching practices in secondary school, based on the indicators of</p>
---	-------------	--	---------------------------	--

the Danielson (2013) framework for teaching. The development of the instrument involved three stages: in the first, the instrument was designed; in the second, evidence of content validity was established; In the third stage, a pilot test was carried out with a sample of 203 secondary school teachers, in order to generate evidence of reliability and

validity related to the construct.

Maribel García
Gracia, Alicia
Razeto Pavez

2019

Why do young people miss school? An exploration of the school experience of absentee students in Catalonia

Original Indexed

The article explores the phenomenon of school absenteeism from a biographical perspective in a group of young people from secondary schools in Catalonia. From a qualitative methodological approach, the vision of young people about their school experience, the meaning they attribute to school and the reasons for

				their school absenteeism is analyzed.
Antonia Valdés, César Coll, Leili Falsafi	2016	Transformative experiences that give us identity as learners: the key learning experiences	Validation Indexed	The objective of this applied descriptive and correlational study was to determine the level of Burnout Syndrome existing in university teachers belonging to the faculty of education, of a private university in Bogotá, and the relationships between said level with variables of gender and seniority. work

and with the coping strategies commonly used by them.

<p>Martha Mora-Torres, Ana Lilia Laureano-Cruces, Perla Velasco-Santos</p>	<p>2019</p>	<p>Structure of emotions within a teaching-learning process</p>	<p>Validation Indexed</p>	<p>This work focuses on the design of an emotional assessment structure developed for an intelligent learning system. This structure will complete the information coming from the user; In this way, it is intended to enhance the effectiveness of the intervention of this intelligent</p>
--	-------------	---	---------------------------	---

learning system through the interface, represented by a pedagogical agent. The importance of emotions in the teaching-learning process is highlighted and a proposal is made that includes a design methodology. The above allows a representation of the emotional state of the user at a given moment.

Gökhan ORHAN, Prof. Dr. Ömer BEYHAN	2020	Teachers’ Perceptions And Teaching	Validatio n Indexed	This study aims to investigate perceptions
---	------	---	-------------------------------	---

Experiences and teaching
 On Distance experiences of
 Education the teachers on
 Through the distance
 Synchronous education
 Video during the
 Conferencin Covid- 19
 g During pandemic. The
 Covid-19 case study
 Pandemic design was
 applied in this
 study. This
 study was
 carried out
 with 15
 teachers. The
 data was
 obtained
 through a
 semi-
 structured
 interview form.

Donald Tagino Hutagaol, Sismudjito, Hadriana Marhaeni Munthe, Rizabuana	2020	Character Building In Students' Deviant Behavior At Sma Negeri	Original Indexed	The objective of the research was to find out and to interpret the social
---	------	---	-------------------------	--

Ismail, Henry Sitorus	1 Kotalimbaru, Deli Serdang, Indonesia	construction of character building in families and schools of the students; The result of the research showed that the students who got problems were usually concerned with lack of character building from their families with various reasons, and one of them is lack of social interaction between the students and their families related to economic problems.
--------------------------	--	---

Indah ayu Johanda Putri	2020	The Effect Of Work Experience And Characteristics Of Jobs On Employee Work Achievement In Shipping Company	Original Indexed	The commitment itself is shaped through individual characteristics and job characteristics. High commitment will improve employee work performance, thus individual characteristics and job characteristics should logically be related to work performance.
Maria CONSTANTINESCU, Georgeta CHIRLEŞAN, Cristina DUMITRU TĂBĂCARU	2020	School Climate And Behaviour Management In Romanian Schools	Validation Indexed	A healthy learning environment is most of the time positively correlated with

a positive
school climate.
The present
article is
aiming to
provide an
overview on
school wide
discipline
prevention in
Romanian
educational
context and to
identify
existing
practices to
support and
prevent school
indiscipline in
order to create
a positive
school
environment
which will
facilitate
learning

Barbosa Ramírez, L., Muñoz Ortega, P., Rueda Villamizar X. & Suárez Leiton, K.	2009	Burnout syndrome and coping strategies in university teachers.	Validatio n Indexed	The objective of this applied descriptive and correlational study was to determine the level of Burnout Syndrome existing in university teachers belonging to the faculty of education, of a private university in Bogotá, and the relationships between said level with variables of gender and seniority. work and with the coping strategies
--	------	---	-------------------------------	--

Barraza Macías, A. & Gracia Álamos, A.,	2015	Proactive coping strategies in the face of the stress generated by the educational reform.	Validation Indexed	commonly used by them. Establish if there is a relationship between the level of stress generated by the educational reform in primary education teachers and the greater or lesser use of proactive coping strategies.
Cabello, R., Ruiz Aranda, & Fernández Berrocal P	2010	Intelligent emotional teachers. Zaragoza, Spain: Interuniversi ty Electronic Journal of Teacher Training.	Indexed	In this article we describe the importance of completing teacher training with the learning and development of social and emotional

aspects. Thus, emotional intelligence (EI), understood as a complement to the cognitive development of teachers and students, enters the educational context. We review the ability model of Mayer & Salovey (1997), some of the socio-emotional improvement programs designed for teachers, and some activities for the development

Gallardo Jaque, Alejandro	2017	The emotional competences in the curriculum of the Pedagogy careers of the University of Playa Ancha.	Systemat yc review Indexed	of EI in teachers. The objective of this work is to elaborate, implement and evaluate a proposal for the incorporation of emotional competences in the curriculum of pedagogy careers at the University of Playa Ancha, with a mixed approach, based on four studies in three years of work. The design is quasi- experimental with pre-test / post-test measures and
------------------------------	------	---	----------------------------------	---

control group in a first study, evaluating the process of applying the program with the experimental groups. In addition to the initial and final evaluation, a process evaluation has been carried out in the experimental groups.

Grinnell, Richard M., Jr.; Yvonne A. Unrau; Margaret Williams	2009	Introduction to Social Work Research	Systematic review Indexed	A comprehensive introduction to the most widely used approach to social work theory and practice. It offers a systematic
---	------	--------------------------------------	----------------------------------	--

overview of
 core theories
 and practice
 issues in
 challenging
 domination
 and
 oppression.

<p>Hernández Reyes, C.L. & Flores Kastanis E. Noviembre,</p>	<p>2011</p>	<p>The role of emotional intelligence in the teaching process of assigning meanings to educational change. Presentation at: XI National Congress of Educational Research.</p>	<p>Systemati c review Indexed</p>	<p>This case study attempts to make a first exploration of the possible relationship between emotional intelligence (EI) and the meaning that teachers give to an experience of educational change</p>
<p>Ibarra Aguirre, E., Armenta Beltrany,</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>Self-concept, coping</p>	<p>Original</p>	<p>The purpose of the study was</p>

M. & Jacobo García, H.M.	strategies and professional teaching performance.	Indexed	to know some of the links between self- concept, coping strategies and the teaching performance of teachers who work in two adverse Mexican contexts with high, and at the same time, relative sociocultural closure.
-----------------------------	---	---------	--

Laboratorio Latinoamericano de Evaluación de la Calidad de la Eucación (LLECE)	2012	Analysis of the school climate: Powerful factor that explains learning in Latin America and	Validatio n Indexed	This document carries out a more in-depth analysis of the different dimensions of the school climate in 3rd and 6th grade,
--	------	---	-------------------------------	--

the
Caribbean ?.

separately. To
achieve this
task, first the
SERCE school
climate index
and the
variables of the
questionnaires
that
theoretically
belonged to
this construct
were analyzed.

Pertegal-Felices, M^a
L., Castejón-Costa,
J. L. & Martínez
Ruiz, M^a. A.

2011

Socioemotio
nal
Competencie
s in Teacher
Professional
Developmen
t

Validatio
n
Indexed

In this paper, a
comparison of
profiles of
socio-
emotional
competences is
carried out,
through a
multivariate
analysis of
variance, for
which the
opinion of a
sample of 148
practicing

teachers and the measurement of these competencies of 139 teaching students was available. The results indicated that there are differences in the profiles of both groups; this difference being significant for 11 of the 13 socio-emotional variables analyzed.

Pérez-González
 Juan Carlos & Pena
 Garrido Mario

2011

Building the science of emotional education. Parents and Teachers.

Original Indexed

In this article, the authors review the concept and justification of emotional

education from a current scientific point of view, indicate the main initiatives of research-based emotional education strategies in Spain, and the ten international recommendations for the design, implementation and evaluation of emotional education programs at sea are presented.

Indexed

Azlin Norhaini
 Mansor, Mohd
 Zabil Ikhsan

2021

The Effects
 of School

Indexed

A school climate is defined as a pattern of

Mohamed
Nasaruddin and
Aida Hanim A.
Hamid.

Climate on
Sixth Form
Teachers'
Self-Efficacy
in Malaysia

shared
perceptions of
the
characteristics
and
atmosphere,
including its
norms, values,
and
expectations of
an organization
with its
members. In
addition, a
school climate
is also defined
as the quality
and character
of school life.

The Aspen Institute

2021

School
Climate
Literature
Summary

Classroom
observations
can also be
used to assess
the extent to
which teachers
are using
instructional

Escalante Mateos
Naira, Fernández-
Zabala Arantza,
Goñi Palacios Eider
and Izar-de-la-
Fuente Díaz-de-
Cerio, Iker. 2021

School
Climate and
Perceived
Academic
Performance
: Direct or
Resilience-
Mediated
Relationship
?

practices that
foster positive
social and
emotional
development,
which is
associated with
classroom
climate.
Modern-day
society is
immersed in a
process of
constant
transformation
, with
numerous
social, cultural,
economic,
political and
technological
changes taking
place in a short
space of time.
These changes
and the needs
derived from
them
constantly

generate new challenges and oblige schools to adopt a dynamic of ongoing transformation, assessment and adaptation.

1. NOTION

The term emotional intelligence appears in psychological literature in 1990, in a writing by American psychologists Peter Salovey and John Mayer. However, it was with the publication of Daniel Goleman's book *Emotional Intelligence* (1995) that the concept spread rapidly.

Mayer & Salovey define emotional intelligence as “the ability to accurately perceive, value and express emotions; the ability to access and generate feelings that facilitate thinking; the ability to understand emotion and emotional awareness; and the ability to regulate emotions and promote emotional and intellectual growth” (Mayer & Salovey, 1997: 10).

In our schools it is no longer enough to achieve a good performance of the students, the success of the teaching staff is also linked to developing people integrated into society, with social and emotional tools that allow them to face the challenges of daily life (Fernández – Berrocal & Ruiz –Aranda, 2008). The learning climate is interaction, communication between those who are within the

teaching - learning process, this must occur between the teacher and the students and viceversa, as well as the student - student.

2. CATEGORIZATION

According to the reading on the subject in question, it is categorized into:

Emotional intelligence:

Which according to Goleman (1995) defines emotional intelligence as: “the ability to recognize our own feelings and those of others, to motivate ourselves and to properly manage relationships.

Teaching Emotional Intelligence:

In our schools it is no longer enough to achieve a good performance of the students, the success of the teaching staff is also linked to developing people integrated into society, with social and emotional tools that allow them to face the challenges of daily life (Fernández – Berrocal & Ruiz –Aranda, 2008). It implies that teachers develop a greater capacity to identify, understand, regulate and think with emotions intelligently, they will have more resources to get students emotionally more prepared and to better cope with stressful events that frequently arise in the educational context.

The third and final category is Classroom Climate:

According to Repetto Talavera (nd), the climate in the classroom should prevail harmony, trust, security, respect, so that students can express themselves freely, make known any concerns or doubts in favor of obtaining true learning, also Within this space, the establishment of norms and rules that will help the proper development of the Teaching and Learning Process is considered.

3. CHARACTERIZATION

Characteristics of the emotionally intelligent teacher:

Socialization, with its emotional aspects, finds a very adequate space in the school environment, as Extremera and Fernández Berrocal (2004) point out, not only because the student remains in the classroom for a large part of their childhood and adolescence, periods in which especially emotional development occurs, but rather because of the number of problems that arise in the educational field (school failure, violence, difficulties in coexistence, etc.), thereby demonstrating once again that the needs raised in educational institutions go beyond promoting the cognitive development of students, aiming to ensure that their students achieve comprehensive training, as one more consequence of the current conception of the role of affectivity and emotions in education, which shows that the cognitive configures the affective and the affective conditions the cognitive (Hernández, 2002).

Characteristic principles of climate in the classroom:

For Rodríguez Vitae (s.f.)

Principle No. 1:

The class environment has to make it possible to get to know all the people in the group and to get closer to each other. Progressively it must make possible the construction of a cohesive human group with common objectives, goals and illusions.

Principle No. 2:

"The school environment has to facilitate everyone's contact with various materials and activities that allow covering a wide range of cognitive, affective and social learning"

Principle No. 3:

"The school environment has to be diverse, having to transcend the idea that all learning takes place within the four walls of the classroom. Different

scenarios should be offered, -whether they are built or natural- depending on the tasks undertaken and the objectives pursued ".

Principle No. 4:

"The school environment has to offer different sub-scenarios in such a way that the people in the group can feel welcomed according to different moods, expectations and interests."

Principle No. 5:

"The environment must be actively built by all the members of the group it welcomes, reflecting their peculiarities, their own identity."

The learning environments will allow constant interactions between student-teacher, student-student, student-experts, guests / community members, student-tools, student-content, student-environment.

4. DIFFERENTIATION

Social competence: According to Caballo (1993), social competence (or social skills) implies the set of behaviors emitted by an individual in an interpersonal context that expresses the feelings, attitudes, desires, opinions or rights of that individual in an appropriate way. the situation, whether in the family, school, work, or other context, respecting those behaviors in others and that, generally, solves the immediate problems that may arise in the interaction, minimizing the probability of future problems appearing.

Emotional competence:

Thus, Gallardo Jaque (2017), mentions that the concept of emotional competence refers to the knowledge, capacities, abilities and attitudes that are considered necessary to understand, express and regulate emotional phenomena appropriately.

5. CLASSIFICATION:

Personal intelligence:

- Awareness in oneself: it is the ability to recognize and understand one's own strengths, weaknesses, moods, emotions and impulses, as well as the effect they have on others and on work.

- Self-regulation or self-control: it is the ability to control our own emotions and impulses to adapt them to a goal, to take responsibility for one's own actions, to think before acting and to avoid premature judgments.

- Self motivation: it is the ability to be in a state of continuous search and persistence in the achievement of objectives, facing problems and finding solutions.

Interpersonal intelligence:

- Empathy: it is the ability to understand the needs, feelings and problems of others, putting oneself in their place, and responding correctly to their emotional reactions.

- Social skills: it is the talent in managing relationships with others, in knowing how to persuade and influence others.

6. BONDING

In 20th century schools, teacher success has been essentially linked to the academic achievements of their students, that is, to school performance. However, the 21st century society has created new demands and challenges for both the School and the teachers who have deeply questioned the current educational principles and objectives.

It implies that teachers develop a greater capacity to identify, understand, regulate and think with emotions intelligently, they will have more resources to get students emotionally more prepared and to better cope with stressful events that frequently arise in the educational context. Our educational system is witnessing a very important process of transformation of the study plans and a modification of the schooling obligatorily oriented towards the integral development of the person centered on competences (LOE, 2006). Unesco, in

its Delors report (1996), proposes different alternatives for 21st century education and emphasizes the role of emotions and the need to educate the emotional demands of the human being together with its cognitive dimension.

The challenge for society and the educational system lies in knowing how to extend this training to all teachers, so that it is not an anecdotal and punctual training in some very specific centers full of healthy romanticism and enthusiasm. A process of change that may seem utopian to some in these years of economic crisis, but that the course of time is turning into an urgent necessity and not a superfluous luxury. To resolve the contradictions and paradoxes of the 21st century society we need a healthy, competent and happy school, and this will be an impossible mission without emotionally intelligent teachers.

7. METHODOLOGY

It is intended to carry out a study of positivist paradigm, within the Technological University of Ciudad Juárez, according to Hernández Sampieri (2014, p. 4), “the quantitative approach uses the collection and analysis of data to refine the research questions or reveal new questions in the interpretation process”. The most representative authors of the chosen paradigm are Galileo, Newton, Comte, Mill, Durkheim and Popper, he has made it clear that the most usual methods are experimental, is positivist, formulates general laws, faithful to neutrality and works by means of statistics. (Bolívar, s.f.)

The methodological approach will be developed through the correlational method, which is used when the purpose is to know the relationship between two or more concepts, categories or variables in a particular context. Associates variables through a predictable pattern for a group of settlers; offer predictions, explain the relationship between variables and quantify these relationships of the variables (Hernández Sampieri, 2014), this method stands out for the present research since it is desired to study the emotional intelligence of

the teacher, as well as the teacher-student relationship and how this affects the development of the learning climate.

8. EXEMPLIFICATION

Examples of the application of emotional intelligence and classroom climate in teaching practice are presented:

- Learning climate molded to the needs of the students.
- Teachers without features of burnout syndrome
- Practice workshops for the identification of teachers who wish to improve their emotional intelligence.
- Practice workshops for the identification of teachers who wish to improve the climate in the classroom.
- Better teacher evaluations.
- Increase in teacher-student, teacher-teacher, student-student motivation.
- Better academic performance in higher education.

DISCUSSION

Given the importance of developing and improving the emotional intelligence of teachers, the following is considered relevant: some of the activities that can be effective emotional intelligence strategies such as the one described above are described and the relationship between these activities and the branches of the theoretical model of emotional intelligence on which is:

- Perception, evaluation and expression of emotions: the development of these skills is linked especially to the recognition of emotions in oneself and in others.
- Emotion as a facilitator of thought: through these skills, emotional events take part in our thinking, guiding the way we process thought information.

- Emotional knowledge: it is necessary to acquire a good emotional vocabulary with which to correctly express our states and thus facilitate communication and therefore social relationships.

- Regulation of emotions: the last activity that we propose refers to the most complex skill of the model, that is, the ability to manage our emotions in given situations, positive and negative, and use the information that emotions provide us based on of their usefulness without repressing or exaggerating the information they carry. All this coupled with the climate in the classroom, the research by Aranda, Cabello and Fernandez-Berrocal (2010) being the most significant.

Conclusions

Being a teacher, like being a person, has become a more difficult task in the 21st century than each of us could have imagined when we began to train as teachers. In this article, the personal and social relevance of completing teacher training with the development of their emotional and social capacities has been highlighted. To do this, in the first place, these skills have been framed and organized from the Emotional Intelligence model of Mayer & Salovey (1997).

The challenge for our society and our educational system lies in knowing how to extend this training to all teachers, so that it is not an anecdotal and punctual training in some very specific centers full of healthy romanticism and enthusiasm. A process of change that may seem utopian to some in these years of economic crisis, but that the course of time is

becoming an imperative need and not a superfluous luxury. To resolve the contradictions and paradoxes of the 21st century society we need a healthy, competent and happy school, and this will be an impossible mission without emotionally intelligent teachers.

For this reason, it is suggested to carry out more research on emotional intelligence and the climate in the classroom in order to fill the research gaps, this could increase the literature on the subject in higher education.

REFERENCES

Azlin Norhaini Mansor, Mohd Zabil Ikhsan Mohamed Nasaruddin and Aida Hanim A. Hamid. (2021). The Effects of School Climate on Sixth Form Teachers' Self-Efficacy in Malaysia. *Sustainability*, 2, 14.

Barbosa Ramírez, L., Muñoz Ortega, P., Rueda Villamizar X. & Suárez Leiton, K. (2009). Síndrome de Burnout y estrategias de afrontamiento en docentes universitarios. *Revista Iberoamericana de Psicología: Ciencia y Tecnología*. 2(1), 21-30.

Barraza Macías, A. & Gracia Álamos, A., (2015). Las estrategias de afrontamiento proactivo ante el estrés generado por la reforma educativa. *Revista Electrónica de Investigación Educativa Sonorense*. VII(17), 51-63.

Bermúdez-Aponte, José Javier; Pedroza Ortíz, Alexandra & Rincon Rivera, Clara Inés., (2015).El clima organizacional en universidades de Bogotá desde la perspectiva de los estudiantes. Ensenada, México: REIDE: Revista Electrónica de Investigación Educativa.

Birch, S. H., & Ladd, G. W. (1996). Interpersonal relationships in the school environment and children's early school adjustment: The role of teachers and peers. In J. Juvonen & K. R. Wentzel (Eds.), *Cambridge studies in social and emotional development. Social motivation: Understanding children's school adjustment* (pp. 199-225). New York, NY, US: Cambridge University Press.

Brackett, M.A., Mayer, J.D. y Warner, R.M. (2004). Emotional intelligence and the prediction of behavior. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 36, 1387-1402

Cabello, R., Ruiz Aranda, & Fernández Berrocal P., (2010). Docentes emocionales inteligentes. Zaragoza, España: Revista Electrónica Interuniversitaria de Formación del Profesorado.

Escalante Mateos Naira, Fernández-Zabala Arantza, Goñi Palacios Eider and De-la-Fuente Díaz-de-Cerio Iker Izar. (2021). School Climate and Perceived Academic Performance: Direct or Resilience-Mediated Relationship?. *Sustainability*, 13, 68.

Extremera, N. y Fernández-Berrocal, P. (2002). La inteligencia emocional en el aula como factor protector de conductas problema: violencia, impulsividad y desajuste emocional. En F. A. Muñoz, B. Molina y F. Jiménez (Eds.) *Actas I Congreso Hispanoamericano de Educación y Cultura de Paz* (pp. 599-605). Editorial Universidad de Granada: Granada.

Extremera, N. y Fernández-Berrocal, P. (2003). La inteligencia emocional en el contexto educativo: Hallazgos científicos de sus efectos en el aula. *Revista de Educación*, 332, 97- 116.

Extremera, N. y Fernández-Berrocal, P. (2004). El papel de la inteligencia emocional en el alumnado: evidencias empíricas. *Electronic Journal of Research of Educational Psychology*, 6 (2), 363-382.

Fernández Berrocal, P. & Ruiz Aranda, D. (2008). La inteligencia emocional en la educación. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*. 6(2), 421-436.

Gallardo Jaque, Alejandro.,(2017). Las competencias emocionales en el currículum de las carreras de Pedagogía de la Universidad de Playa Ancha. Chile: Universitat de Girona.

Grinnell, Richard M., Jr.; Yvonne A. Unrau; Margaret Williams (2009). *Introduction to Social Work Research*: F.E. Peacock Publishers. Pp. 452.

Guerrero Barona, E. (2002). Modelo de afrontamiento de estrés laboral en una muestra de docentes universitarios. *Revista Interuniversitaria de Formación del Profesorado*. Núm 43, 93-112.

Guerrero Barona, E. (2003). Análisis pormenorizado de los grados de burnout y afrontamiento del estrés docente en profesorado universitario. *Anales de psicología*. 19(1), 146-156.

Hernández Reyes, C.L. & Flores Kastanis E. Noviembre, (2011). *El papel de la inteligencia emocional en el proceso docente de asignar significados a un cambio educativo*. Ponencia en: XI Congreso Nacional de Investigación Educativa. Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey.

Hernández Sampieri, R., Fernández Collado, C., Baptista Lucio, P., Méndez Valencia, S. Y Mendoza Torres, C. P. Metodología de la investigación. 2014. México, D.F.: McGraw-Hill Education.

Ibarra Aguirre, E., Armenta Beltrany, M. & Jacobo García, H.M. (2014). Autoconcepto, estrategias de afrontamiento y desempeño docente profesional. Estudio comparativo en profesores que trabajan en contextos adversos. *Revista de Currículum y Formación de Profesorado*. 18(1), 223-239.

Laboratorio Latinoamericano de Evaluación de la Calidad de la Educación (LLECE), (2012). Análisis del clima escolar: ¿Poderoso factor que explica el aprendizaje en América Latina y el Caribe?. Madrid, España: Oficina Regional de Educación para América Latina y el Caribe.

Mayer, J. D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is emotional intelligence? In P. Salovey & D. J. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional development and emotional intelligence: Educational implications* (pp. 3-34). New York: Harper Collins.

Mayer, J.D., Salovey, P. y Caruso, D. (2000). Models of emotional intelligence. En R.J. Sternberg (ed.), *Handbook of intelligence* (pp. 396-420). New York: Cambridge.

Marsollier, Roxana y Aparicio, Miriam., (2011). El bienestar psicológico en el trabajo y su vinculación con el afrontamiento en situaciones conflictivas. Viña del Mar, Chile: Psicoperspectivas.

Palomera, R., Fernández-Berrocal, P. y Brackett, M. (2008). La inteligencia emocional como una competencia básica en la formación inicial de

los docentes: algunas evidencias. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 14.

Pertegal-Felices, M^a L., Castejón-Costa, J. L. & Martínez Ruiz, M^a. A. (2011). Competencias Socioemocionales en el Desarrollo Profesional del Maestro. *Educación XXI*.14(2), 237-260.

Pérez-González Juan Carlos & Pena Garrido Mario (2011). Construyendo la ciencia de la educación emocional. *Padres y Maestros*. (342)

Repetto Talavera, E. & Pena Garrido, M. (2010). Las competencias socioemocionales como factor de calidad en la Educación. *REICE. Revista Iberoamericana sobre Calidad, Eficacia y Cambio en Educación*. 8(5), 82-95.

Rodríguez Vitae, Hugo. (s.f.). Ambientes de aprendizaje. 27 de mayo de 2020, de Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Hidalgo Sitio web: <https://www.uaeh.edu.mx/scige/boletin/huejutla/n4/e1.html#refe0>

Ruelas Ibarra, J. (Marzo, 03). *Influencia de competencias emocionales en el desempeño académico de estudiantes del nivel medio superior*. Ponencia en: XI Congreso Nacional de Investigación Educativa. Centro de Estudios Tecnológicos del Mar. Guaymas, Sonora.

Ruiz Bolívar, C. (s.f.) Resumen de la ponencia. Foro: Enfoque Cuantitativo y Cualitativo de la Investigación: Más allá de los paradigmas de Investigación. Recuperado de: www.geocities.com/capeCanavera/Hall/4609/page9.html

Ruiz-Aranda, D., Fernández-Berrocal, P., Cabello, R. y Extremera, N. (2006). Inteligencia emocional percibida y consumo de tabaco y alcohol en adolescentes. *Ansiedad y estrés*, 12 (2-3), 223-230.

Ruiz-Aranda, D., Fernández-Berrocal, P., Cabello, R. y Salguero, N. (2008). Educando la inteligencia emocional en el aula: Proyecto Intemo. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 14.

Sutton, R. & Wheatley, K. (2003). “Teachers’ emotions and teaching: A review of the literature and directions for future research”. *Educational Psychology Review*, 15, 327–358.

Sijtsma, K. (2009). On the use, the misuse and the very limited of the Cronbach’s Alpha. *Psychometrika*, 74(1) 107-120. DOI: 10.1007/S11336-008-9101-0

The Aspen Institute. (2021). School Climate Literature Summary. Education & Society Program, 1, 8. may, 20, 2021, The Aspen Institute Data Base.